

5. SEAGRASS HABITATS

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5.1 Introduction

Seagrasses are a group of permanent flowering plants (angiosperm) that live in marine or brackish environments. There are 4 plant families that are known to exist - Posidoniaceae, Zosteraceae, Hydrocharitaceae, and Cymodoceaceae. Seagrasses reproduce by flowering and producing seeds. These vascular plants usually grow on sandy sediments on the sea bottom, attached by roots and rhizomes, which help stabilize the bottom substrata. Seagrasses are found in patches, these patches can expand to form specific underwater landscapes known as seagrass beds or seagrass meadows. The depth at which seagrasses occur is limited by light availability. Such communities provide habitats to smaller marine animals as nursery areas or shelters. Occurrence of seagrass meadows worldwide within coastal areas decreases due to human disturbances and extreme weather events. Losses in seagrasses can occur when plants are uprooted, smothered or buried by sediments, or through changes in the local environment such as changes to light availability, water temperature or salinity.

Seagrasses are currently experiencing a worldwide decrease in spatial distribution (Short and Wyllie-Echeverria 1996; Short and Coles; 2001; Duarte, 2002; Orth et al., 2006; Anton et al., 2009). Loss or decline of seagrass beds and meadows due to storm impacts is one of the key mechanisms that has been identified amongst various factors that could affect seagrasses (Patriquin 1975; Clarke and Kirkman 1989; Poiner et al. 1989; Shepherd et al. 1989; Kirkman and Kuo, 1990; Short et al. 1991; Preen et al., 1995; Short and Wyllie-Echeverria 1996; Short and Neckles 1999; Westphalen et al., 2004; Fourqurean and Rutten, 2004; Cardoso et al., 2008; Cabaço et al., 2008; Anton et al., 2009).

In general, the impacts of storms on communities can be divided into two groups – direct and indirect. Direct impacts are related to influence of winds, sediment flows, waves and currents, as well as their effects on roots, rhizomes, bodies, leaves, blades, and seeds. Indirect impacts are associated with changes in water quality which result in deterioration of life conditions for seagrasses and eventually have negative impact upon existing seagrass communities.

Uprooting, leaf killing, burial, erosion and abrading of seeds are attributed to direct impacts, while light attenuation, salinity and temperature changes are attributed to indirect impacts. However some of impacts can be attributed to factors other than storms. For instance, light attenuation could be an effect of re-suspension of bottom sediments or plankton blooms; salinity changes could be an effect of influx of saline waters into river mouths and deltas/firths or rainfall producing abnormal runoff. In this report the negative effects of environmental changes on seagrass communities is considered along with how these communities will respond to changes in surrounding environment. Finally, studies that describe how particular storms/hurricanes have affected seagrass communities are presented. Studies on hurricanes have been used as the impacts from such events are likely to be similar to the types of impacts caused by future extreme events.

Severe reduction in populations of benthic fish species at sites covered by decaying seagrasses has been reported by Thomas et al. (1961). Massive disturbance of seagrass beds due to hurricanes are reported by Stoddard (1963), Tabb and Jones (1962). Heck et al. (1996) report substantial seagrass loss after Hurricane Opal in Santa Rosa Sound, Florida. However, hurricanes do not always damage to seagrass meadows, for example Byron and Heck (2006) conducted two field surveys after hurricanes Ivan and Katrina in order to trace post-hurricane changes in seagrasses, species composition, abundance and shoot density were all analyzed and it was concluded that reductions in shoot density could represent normal seasonal variation.

Excessive water movement during storms alters the sediment regime, and also causes mechanical damage to plants. Cambridge et al. (1986) observed the most significant loss of seagrass and attributed this loss to strong wave action. Anton et al. (2009) studied impact of hurricane Katrina on seagrass communities and show that hurricane Katrina did not have a major impact on the community structure (abundance of producers and consumers) and the metabolic functioning of the bed studied (primary and net production and respiration) within one year of landfall. Robbins and Bell (2000) point out that seagrass landscapes are characterized by high seasonal dynamics, however, remain stable annually, while losses and gains of all seagrass patch types within a season were attributed to transitions from species to bare sediment that occur across all depths.

5.2 Uprooting

In general, storm waves and currents cause sediment movements, which either bury plants, or expose roots and rhizomes and even uproot entire plants (Kirkman and Kuo, 1990; Preen et al., 1995). Uprooting of shallow rhizomes during winter storms could be a mechanism for landscape degradation from seagrass beds to bare sediment (Kirkman and Kuo, 1990). Severe storm events can result in uprooting and burial of entire populations accompanied by shifting sediment (Preen et al., 1995; Moncreiff et al., 1999). Fonseca and Bell (1998) examined the relationship between seagrass landscape pattern and physical variables (wind/wave exposure), and found that there is a good correlation. Large-scale uprooting results in formation of grass-free depressions within seagrass beds, known as "blowouts" (Hoskin, 1963), "sand holes" (Ginsburg, 1956), "pot holes" (Thomas et al., 1961) and "grass-free cusps" (Kelly and Conrod, 1973). It is widely suggested that erosion leading to their initial formation can be due to storm waves (Patriquin, 1975). When the density of seagrasses is high strong disturbances cannot erode the bottom. Nevertheless, once the seagrass mat is disrupted via uprooting during storms exposing roots, even normal wave activity is sufficient to continue erosion (Patriquin, 1975). Preen et al. (1995) reported that shallow water seagrass recovery after severe storm and flood events can take ten or more years, this observation was supported by Kirkman (1978); Birch and Birch (1984); Hyland et al. (1989) and Poiner et al. (1989).

5.3 Leaf killing

Massive loss of leaf material in Biscayne Bay after Hurricane Donna was reported by Thomas, et al. (1961) and Tabb and Jones (1962). Due to hurricane Andrew old seagrass blades were still intact, but in some areas the storm had snapped off grass blades, as thick deposit of seagrass blades and other storm-eroded material was observed on the offshore reef shelf. (Tilmant et al., 1994).

5.4 Burial, erosion and abrading of seeds

The effects of storms and hurricanes on seagrass landscapes results in significant changes in sedimentary dynamics and can lead to burial and erosion (Cabaço and Santos, 2007; Cabaço et al., 2008). Burial results in a decrease of the available photosynthetic area (Cabaço et al., 2008), shoot density (Cabaço and Santos, 2007) and ultimately a reduction seagrass meadow area (Kirkman, 1978). Burial and erosion of seagrass can also be caused by migration of sandbars (Marbà et al., 1994, Frederiksen et al., 2004). A study in Florida after hurricane Andrew found a tan/brownish sediment layer deposited on the seagrasses, which was up to 50 cm thick, resulting in substantial damage to the seagrass meadow (Tilmant et al., 1994). In a different study Fourqurean and Rutten (2004) observed burial up to 50 cm after hurricane Georges in Florida. Steward et al. (2006) reported a partial burial of seagrass in Florida (*Halodule wrightii*) observed after hurricanes Frances, Ivan, and Jeanne and mentioned that there was no long-term hurricane effect on the depth-limit coverage of seagrass. The nearshore area, described by Steward et al. (2006) where *Halodule wrightii* had been buried was fully recovered by summer 2005. Laboratory experiment conducted by Cabaço and Santos (2007) confirmed that shoots did not survive more than 2 weeks under complete burial. Cabaço et al. (2008) studied burial thresholds for the 15 seagrass species, as studied levels of shoot mortality due to burial – 50% and 100%. Cabaço et al. (2008) concluded that *Posidonia australis* was the

most tolerant seagrass species to burial, while *Thalassia testudinum* was the most tolerant species to erosion. Burial after hurricane and flood events can affect seeds in shallow water as well, which resulted in slowing-down of recovery process (Preen et al., 1995). Seagrasses can alter both water and sediment flow during low and high energy events. Thus meadows act as a bluff body, modifying the sediment flow pattern, which in turn causes burial of meadows (Granata et al., 2001). Erosion leads to the exposure of the belowground parts of the plants to wave and current action. Such a situation affects the anchoring capacity of the species, and consequently the plants may be more easily detached from the substrate (Cabaço et al., 2008). Intense wave motion during storms and floods causes seagrass seeds to die after being abraded by the churning sediments (Preen et al., 1995).

5.5 Light attenuation

Seagrasses as a vegetation group have higher demands for light in comparison to other terrestrial and marine vegetation – an average of 11% of surface light (Duarte, 1991; Dennison et al., 1993; Abal et al., 1994). However, there is a wide variation in light requirements of individual species and therefore these have different survival thresholds, varying from less than a month to more than 5 months in near-darkness (Gordon et al., 1994; Lee and Dunton, 1997; Longstaff and Dennison, 1999; Longstaff et al., 1999).

Several authors have shown that light availability is an essential factor in determining the depth that seagrasses survive (Cambridge et al., 1986; Dennison et al., 1993; Abal and Dennison, 1996; Steward, et al., 2006). Extreme hydro-meteorological events including extreme run-off of rivers, flooding and storm activity can be a significant indirect cause for seagrass meadow damage through light attenuation (Dennison et al. 1993; Preen et al. 1995; Abal and Dennison 1996).

Tilmant et al. (1994) reported that increased turbidity due to both post-storm plankton bloom and suspended sediments in the areas of the direct impact of hurricane Andrew in Florida affected seagrasses for a long period. Robbins and Bell (2000) studying Tampa Bay have shown how the re-suspension of sediments via summer storm-induced waves and the subsequent release of adsorbed nutrients into the water column, caused phytoplankton blooms and crucially light reduction in the water column. However Cambridge et al. (1986) concluded that increased light attenuation due to phytoplankton blooms and localized suspension of particulate matter in Cockburn Sound, Australia, was not the primary cause of extensive loss of seagrass meadows. Steward et al. (2006) studying impact of hurricanes Frances, Ivan, and Jeanne on seagrass in Florida showed that increased colour and turbidity due to wind-wave sediment re-suspension was observed not only after the storms in September but till mid October 2004.

At the landscape scale, resilience of seagrass meadows is considered by some authors to be a function of both the long-term trends in light availability and their ability to survive pulsed turbidity events (Moore et al., 1997; Longstaff et al., 1999). Such turbidity events may also be reinforced due to abnormal erosion and re-suspension of sediments from logged, cleared or agricultural land during storms (Preen et al., 1995).

Seagrass species demonstrate several morphological and physiological changes due to adaptations to light deprivation, although scale of response and time for adaptation are widely dependent on the particular genus as well as length of lightless period and other ecological conditions such as water temperature, nutrient availability, salinity etc. (Bulthuis, 1983a, b; Gordon et al., 1994; Van Lent et al., 1995; Abal and Dennison, 1996; Grice et al., 1996). Such morphological and physiological adaptations may include increased chlorophyll content, increased canopy height and shoot thinning (Abal et al., 1994; Czerny and Dunton, 1995; Van Lent et al., 1995; Lee and Dunton, 1997). Additional cellular-level changes may also incorporate reductions in $\delta^{13}C$ values as well as decreases in chlorophyll a/b ratios as observed by Longstaff and Dennison (1999).

5.6 Salinity and temperature

Changes in water quality and physical disturbance can reduce the extent of submersed aquatic vegetation worldwide (Bayley et al., 1978; Duarte, 1995; Short and Wyllie-Echeverria, 1996; Valiela et al., 1997). Thompson (1976, 1978) reported seagrass density decline in the Vero segments when salinities dropped due to the influence of discharges from North, Main, and South canals. Montague and Ley (1993) observed that fluctuating salinities affected seagrass abundance in Florida Bay while Robbins and Bell (2000) showed that seagrass distribution is strongly related to salinity zonation. Phillips (1960) found that there is a great amount of leaf kill and fragmentation associated with extremes of temperature. Cambridge et al. (1986) hypothesised that a significant change in the water temperature can cause metabolic stress or potentially allow the invasion of a pathogen. A study by Steward et al. (2006) on the effects of continually low salinities in between 2004-2005 caused by storm winds or waves in Indian River Lagoon on 7 species of sea grass (*Halodule wrightii*, *Syringodium filiforme*, *Thalassia testudinum*, *Halophila johnsonii*, *Halophila decipiens*, *Halophila engelmannii*, and *Ruppia maritima*) found negative trends in densities for all species. Steward et al. (2006) found a strong positive correlation between seagrass abundance and salinity and noted that the lowest salinities during 2004–2006 were measured at those transects where the lowest average densities and emergence of *Ruppia maritima* were observed. At one of transects, there was a transient shift in seagrass species composition and a continued decline in density was observed all over the central Indian River Lagoon. Finally, Steward et al. (2006) concluded that negative effects of low salinities on seagrasses cannot be attributable exclusively to the hurricanes.

To understand how acute salinity pulses due to major storm events can drive change in biomass and distribution pattern of key species and affect restoration, Doering et al. (2001) and Frazer et al. (2006) conducted series of manipulative experiments on *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *Hydrilla verticillata*, and *Vallisneria americana*. *Vallisneria americana* plants were gradually exposed to a salinity of 18‰ for varying times (Doering et al., 2001). Shoot numbers and blade densities decreased relative to control plants (base salinity of 3‰) only after exposures of 20 days or longer. *M.spicatum*, *H.verticillata*, and *V.americana* were subjected to salinities of <1‰ (control), 5‰, 15‰, and 25‰ for 1, 2, and 7 d (Frazer et al., 2006) and then remained in recovery for 28 days following simulated salinity pulses. Frazer et al. (2006) concluded that short-term (1–7 d) exposures to salinities of 15‰ or 25‰ significantly affected growth and survival of *V.americana*, *H.verticillata*, and *M.spicatum*. Measures of growth for those three species decreased significantly, except for elongation of blades in *V.americana* following 1-d or 2-d exposures to 15‰ and addition of turions by *H.verticillata* in all treatments. *H.verticillata* was particularly sensitive to higher salinities (all plants died following even 1-d exposures to 15‰). All *V.americana* and *M.spicatum* plants survived 1-d and 2-d exposures to 15‰, 25‰, but to 100% of these plants died following exposures of 7 d to 15‰ or 1, 2, or 7 d to 25‰.

According to Twilley and Barko (1990) *M.spicatum* can withstand salinities up to 15‰, but Haller et al. (1974) noted that plants stopped growing when exposed to 13.32‰ and died when exposed to 16.65‰ for 4 wk. *H.verticillata* plants did not grow in 6.66‰ and died when exposed to 10‰ (Haller et al. 1974).

Connell (1978) and Sousa (1979) observed that in Kings Bay, Florida, *M.spicatum* recovered more quickly than did *H.verticillata* after Hurricane Elena, and *V.americana* appeared to be largely unaffected by acute disturbance. Terrell and Canfield (1996) attributed precipitous declines in *H.verticillata* Kings Bay during March and April 1993 to a catastrophic storm, the “Storm of the Century,” while *V.americana* and *M.spicatum* were not immediately affected by this storm.

After Frazer et al. (2006) during hurricanes Ivan, Frances, and Jeanne salinities near the bottom increased markedly reaching maxima of 14‰, 14‰, and 19‰, respectively. Duration of pulses was about 24h. Hurricanes altered the biomass and percent cover of submersed aquatic vegetation in Kings Bay. Mean above ground biomass of all submersed aquatic vegetation was significantly reduced (51%) from the pre-

storm sampling period. The mean percent cover reduced to 33% from the pre-storm estimate. *M.spicatum* was particularly affected (83% decrease in aboveground biomass and mean cover declined by 79.8%); *H.verticillata* also declined significantly after the storms (47% in aboveground biomass and mean cover declined by 15.0%).

5.7 Habitat resilience and recovery

Seagrass communities demonstrate a large variety of adaptive methods to negative or harmful environmental influences, such as extreme hydro-meteorological events. Generally, the differences in the susceptibility and adaptation of different macrophytes to storm damage, is a result of variations in the architecture of the plants (Fourqurean and Rutten, 2004), these variations are likely to be a result of different life-history strategies (Bazzaz, 1979).

Khoel (1984) studied how organisms with different morphology defect in moving water, (with a focus on two consequences; deformation and breakage), it was found that there are different mechanisms by which organisms can withstand the water flow. Many organisms can thrive at wave or current-sweep sites because of their particular life history strategies. Understanding the rate and mechanisms of seagrass meadow recovery from natural disturbances is essential for both scientific purposes and proper guiding for restoration and management of damaged seagrass ecosystems (Fourqurean and Rutten, 2004).

Adaptive modifications of eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) communities at the landscape scale have been reported by Frederiksen et al. (2004) at Vejle fjord along the Danish coast. Elongation, intricate outline and reduced aggregation of patch shapes have been observed as adoptions to wave dynamics. Overall, the study showed that shallow-water eelgrass populations form characteristic landscapes with a configuration that is highly related to the level of physical exposure and that the size and position of eelgrass beds change substantially among years.

Studies by Olesen and Sand-Jensen (1994b) Fonseca (1996), Fonseca and Bell (1998), Ramage and Schiel (1999) and Fonseca et al. (2000) have revealed that aggregation of communities makes them more resistant to external disturbances than patchy populations and is thought to be due to better substrate cohesion by plant roots/rhizomes and minimized patch edge exposure to wave and current activity. It is thought that mutual protection is much more efficient in large patches, which results in reduced seagrass mortality during negative hydro-meteorological events and therefore populations in the largest patches have the greatest resilience to physical disturbances. However, a study by Frederiksen et al. (2004) showed that this statement is valid only when the impact of particular disturbance is spatially variable. If the whole seagrass landscape is affected by a particular negative physical influence (e.g. storm), spatial pattern and patch size is unlikely to influence resilience. Finally, authors suggest that extrinsic disturbance constantly keeps populations in a state of continuous recolonization.

Results obtained from other studies, such as those conducted by Thomas et al. (1961) indicate that certain seagrass communities (e.g. those of *Thalassia testudium*), may recover very quickly from storm damage thanks to rapid re-growth. Hence, authors believe that direct physical impacts are less harmful in comparison to those associated with freshwater run-off and consequent salinity alteration.

According to some authors (e.g. Zieman, 1976; Rollon et al., 1998), the period required for seagrass meadows to recover from a disturbance is a function of the size of the disturbance. The recovery dynamics are also greatly influenced by the size of area affected and its interaction with the reproductive strategies of the species (Sousa 1984; Pickett and White, 1985; Fahrig et al., 1994). Based on results from this author, obtained from a 5-year monitoring survey regarding flood and hurricane impact upon more than 1000 sq. km of seagrass meadows in Australia, combined with results from previous studies by Kirkman (1978), Birch and Birch (1984), Hyland et al. (1989), Poiner et al. (1989) and Preen (1994), Preen et al. (1995) it

can be concluded that recovery would take up to 10 years. According to Zieman (1976) and Rollon et al. (1998) such a long recovery period resulting from uprooting and bottom-sediment erosion is due to the fact that re-colonization often takes place via vegetative growth instead of through seedling recruitment. However, if instead damages result from burial and thinning, recovery may be much faster and take from a few months up to 1-3 years, depending on the species (Fourqurean and Rutten, 2004).

The pioneer role in the re-colonization is attributed to seagrasses that combine a relatively high reproductive output with a high dispersal capacity and large seeds (Olesen et al., 2004). Early colonizers of disturbed areas are often small seagrass species which show faster rhizome extension rates than large ones (Marbà and Duarte 1998), and play a pioneer role in the re-colonization process (den Hartog 1971; Kirkman, 1985; Brouns, 1987; Duarte, 1991; Walker et al., 1999). However, small, fast-growing species may not act as early colonizers when dealing with large-scale disturbances (Olesen et al., 2004). Germination from seed bank reserves and seedling recruitment are also essential to seagrass habitat recovery (Birch and Birch, 1984; Preen et al., 1995). Recolonization after severe disturbances involving total losses of vegetation requires seed reserves since re-colonization process must necessarily involve dispersal processes delivering seeds to initiate patches far inside the disturbed areas (Olesen et al., 2004). Finally, Preen et al. (1995) warn that a few small isolated plants at a site may not always be indicative of a recovering seagrass bed.

5.8 Positive features of storm disturbance to natural seagrass landscape dynamics

Several authors report positive consequences from storm disturbance over longer-term time periods. Patriquin (1975) suggests that disturbance helps maintain rich diversity in mixed seagrass meadows. According to Sousa (1984) and Pickett and White (1985) release of uprooted areas as a result of negative hydro-meteorological events eventually provides space for the subsequent establishment of new individuals, and where disturbances recur more frequently, high species richness is maintained (Olesen et al., 2004). Some authors (e.g. Zieman et al., 1989) even suggest that periodic removal of sediments, organic matter and biomass by storms can be necessary for the long-term homeostasis of some seagrass beds. Kirkman and Kuo (1990) based on three case studies have come to the conclusion that disturbances play important role in preventing climax species to completely dominate seagrass communities in shallow areas exposed to local winds and deeper places exposed to ocean swell.